

REPUBLIQUE DU MALI
Un Peuple - Un But - Une Foi

Ministère de la Santé et des Affaires Sociales

The Malian Action Plan (The MAP)

2020 - 2023
Leading The Way

100%
100%
50%
PLUS

January 2020

Foreword

Every Malian has a right to good health and human security. It is a deep respect for these rights, and desire to protect them, which has inspired the Mali Action Plan (MAP).

The MAP is a bold vision for transformative change. It aims to accelerate Mali's progress toward the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and towards universal health care. Its goals are aligned with those of the CREDD and the PRODESS and build upon past reforms and ongoing efforts across sectors.

The priorities of the MAP are radically improving health indicators, with women and children at its core, and delivering results quickly. The MAP strives to build a health system that is equitable and inclusive by removing barriers and working with and for communities. Its work will be oriented towards bringing services to the Last Mile and ensuring no one is left behind.

It will advance all aspects of service quality – from infrastructure to training – to improve the demand and confidence of the Malian people in their health system. This work must save lives today and be sustained for generations.

The MAP will learn and draw inspiration from other countries but will be rooted in the Malian culture and context, responsive to the particular needs of different locations and populations. It takes a system-level approach by pushing for efficiency, integration, coordination, and capacity building throughout the health system and through strong international partnerships.

Our country is being stressed to the breaking point by the forces of unrest, migration, population growth, climate change, and urbanization. We must take decisive, timely action. Strengthening the health system will help to heal our communities and renew bonds of trust, promoting peace and stability.

Friends, colleagues I leave you with this most urgent call to arms. The MAP is an opportunity to unlock the potential of our country, to fight for social justice, to unite it around a vision of a better future.

The time to act is now. Join us.

Executive summary

Mali's population health indicators are alarming, particularly around issues of maternal health, sexual reproductive health, and child survival. Regional forces, including demographic change, instability, and climate change, are further straining the country's health system.

In response to these challenges, the Minister of Health and Social Affairs (MOHSA) of Mali has developed an ambitious vision for the transformation of the Malian health sector: The Mali Action Plan (the MAP). This builds upon the reform launched in February 2019 and is aligned with the Strategic Framework for Economic Development (CREDD) and National Health Sector Strategic Plan (PRODESS). Through the MAP, Mali aims to become the first country to nationalize and implement the Global Action Plan for Healthy Lives and Well-being for All. It will also begin a dramatic turnaround in the health of its people, striving to achieve the greatest improvement in key health indicators in Africa by 2023. This is captured in the 100 – 100 – 50 – PLUS vision: a plan to double-down on access and maximize impact at all levels.

The MAP's design and implementation will also be guided by the principles of equity and inclusion, innovation, community, integration, results-based financing, strong national leadership and ownership, and mutual accountability. It will strive to utilize the best international practices and adapt them to the local context, drawing lessons from what did and did not work.

Over the next few years, the MAP will initiate the restructuring of four major pillars of the healthcare sector: the primary health care system, the secondary health care system, the diagnostic and laboratory services, and the pharmacy procurement and distribution system.

- The primary health care pillar consists of forming a world-class national cadre of professionalized community health workers (CHWs), rehabilitating and digitizing the entire community health center (CSCoM) network, setting up a Model Family Cluster program, and establishing a Center of Excellence in Primary Health Care.
- The secondary health care pillar includes initiating a comprehensive reform of the hospital referral system, called the "1 plus 7 hospital referral network," starting with the ongoing rehabilitation of the Gabriel Touré teaching hospital in Bamako. It also includes launching a new surgery skills initiative to boost life-saving surgery capacity at selected hospitals.
- A focus on the national laboratory and diagnostic services make up the third pillar of the MAP, which consists of rehabilitating the entire system's infrastructure and processes, improving synergies with the private sector, exploring the creation of the first rapid diagnostic test (RDT) manufacturing line in the region in Bamako, and strengthening the newly created National Institute of Public Health (NPHI).
- Finally, the pharmaceutical and medical consumable procurement and supply chain services form the fourth MAP pillar. This consists of overhauling the public procurement system (the PPM) and developing new last mile delivery logistics solutions to reach CHWs, CSCoMs, and referral centers.

This fundamental transformation of the Malian healthcare system will be carried out using strategic MAP Delivery Approaches. First is a commitment to Last Mile service delivery - reaching people in their community with the services they need. Second is using differentiated approaches to healthcare, which are responsive to location and population characteristics. These should be responsive to distinctive regional needs, such as improving resilience in the North and Center, and consolidating the health system in the South. Third, the MAP will deliver rapid impact interventions for priority populations, targeting the risk factors and disease priorities of mothers, children under the age of five, as well as youth in the second decade of life. Fourth, the MAP will have integrated fiduciary management, carried out by a new MAP Basket Fund responsible for the transparent distribution, accounting, audit, and financial reporting of donor funds. This will provide better coordinated, integrated, and efficient use of existing funds and help to mobilize new funding. Finally, the MAP's strategy and operations will be driven by a dedicated MAP Management Unit, empowered by and reporting directly to the Minister of Health and Social Affairs.

Other critical dimensions that will enable the MAP's implementation include: broadening the range of health financing approaches, including national health insurance systems; asking for increased commitments from international partners to the MAP; improving governance at the MOHSA and among Community Health Associations (ASACO); engaging strategically with the private sector; and testing and deploying health technologies and innovations.

The MAP constitutes an unprecedented opportunity to improve the health of the Malian people, to invest in their human capital, security, and resilience, and to fundamentally transform the country for this and future generations.

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1. Context

1.1 The Health Situation in Mali

The Malian public healthcare system is organized in three tiers. At the base is the primary healthcare system, which is made-up of 1,346 community health centers (CSCoMs). CSCoMs are privately managed non-profit entities owned by communes and managed by community health associations (ASACO). The second tier is composed 63 referral facilities known as Centres de santé de référence (CsRef) or District Hospitals, as well as 7 regional public hospitals (Établissements Publics Hospitaliers – EPH). Finally, the top tier of the health system offers advanced care through five major publics or teaching hospitals, of which three are general hospitals (l’Hôpital Point G, Centre Hospitalo-Universitaire Gabriel Touré and l’Hôpital du Mali) and two are sub-specialized (National Centre for Odontology and Stomatology, and the Tropical Ophthalmology Institute of Africa).

Figure 1: Sanitary map of Mali, 2011

In addition to the public system, a parallel private sector plays an important role in the provision of health services, but this sector currently lacks adequate regulations and supervision.

Health Indicators

Mali’s health outcomes are deeply concerning. Although improvements have been achieved over the past two decades, maternal mortality in Mali remains unacceptably high and among the worst in the

region, with a rate of 325 deaths per 100,000 live births. ¹ This persists despite national efforts to improve maternal health in recent years, including policies to provide free Caesarean sections (2005), free malaria prevention and treatment services for pregnant women (2010), and the required notification of maternal deaths (2017). The latest EDSM estimates the lifetime risk of maternal death to be 0.021, meaning that, given current national conditions, roughly one woman in fifty is at risk of dying from childbirth during her reproductive life. ¹

Mali has the highest adolescent age-specific fertility rate in the world, with 36% of female adolescents aged 15 to 19 having already given birth in 2018. Regional disparities are notable, with the proportion of girls in this age group with a child being the highest in Kayes and Koulikoro (41.5% and 35.9%, respectively), compared to only 20.3% in Bamako. Education and poverty are also determining factors, with nearly 40% of girls without any schooling having given birth before age 19, versus 17.3% among those with secondary education. Similarly, 28.1% of girls in the poorest quintiles had begun their reproductive life, while 20.7% of those in the wealthiest quintile had done so. The number of women age 15-49 using modern contraceptive methods is very low, despite increasing from 6% in 2001 to 16% nationally in 2018. The same regional disparities are found, with Kidal and Gao having very low contraception coverage rates (2.6% and 3.3%, respectively), compared to Bamako (22.3%). ¹

After thirty years of steady decline, the child mortality rate in Mali remains high compared to other countries in the region and was found to have increased between 2012 and 2018, from a rate of 95 to one of 101 deaths per 1,000 live births. ¹ This may be related to an underestimation of the 2012 rate due to data collection difficulties in areas with challenging security conditions (Segou, Kayes, Timbuktu, and Mopti), which are also zones where children under-five are most at risk of dying. Important national variations in the rate of under-five mortality have been observed between economic quintiles, with the highest risk of mortality in the lowest quintile (143 ‰) compared to the highest quintile (57 ‰); as well as between rural and urban areas (111 ‰ and 61 ‰ respectively). ¹

Figure 2: Maternal and Under 5 Mortality Rates

Source: EDSM III, IV, V and VI ¹

Malnutrition indicators also remain persistently high despite improvements since 2001. The percentage of children with stunted growth in Mali in 2018 was 27%, with especially high stunting prevalence (above 30%) found in Sikasso, Mopti, and Gao, as well as among the poorest children (33% among the poorest quintile). Nearly a fifth of all children under-five are malnourished (19%) and a tenth suffer from emaciation (9%).¹ These problems are pervasive, with dietary iron deficiency being the most important health problem leading to disability in the country, not just among children but people of all ages, and malnutrition being the number one risk factor driving death and disability combined in the country.²

Vaccination coverage among children 12-23 months-old has been variable but low in the past two decades. The percentage of children who received all the basic vaccines increased from 29% to 48% between 2001 and 2006, but later decreased to 39% in 2012 and increased to 45% in 2018. Coverage rates also differ widely between regions due to conditions on the ground hampering access, with the highest coverage rates recorded in Ségou (52%) and the lowest in the regions of Gao (22%) and Kidal (less than 1%).¹

With about 65,000 Daily Adjusted Live Years (DALYs) lost per 100,000 population, Mali is among the five countries with the largest burden of diseases in the world.³ While the share of non-communicable diseases has been increasing since the 1990s (particularly stroke and ischemic heart disease), communicable, neonatal, maternal and nutritional diseases still account for about 73% of the overall burden, which is a higher share than what is found in other West Africa or low income countries.³

Malaria and diarrheal disease are the largest causes of death from infectious disease in the country. Mali's malaria incidence rate has been rising over the past two decades, and at an estimated 84 new cases per 1,000 in 2018, is among the highest in the world.⁴ Among children under five, malaria is responsible for nearly a quarter of all deaths.

The incidence rate of tuberculosis has been declining steadily since 2001, but is still high, at 53 per 100,000 people.⁵ HIV incidence rates were found to have increased between 2012 and 2018, reaching 0.78 per 1,000 people, a trend making Mali an outlier in the region.⁶ (see figure 3)

Figure 3: HIV, TB and Malaria Incidence

Source: Malaria (Ministry of Health), TB (WHO), HIV (UNAIDS)

Health System Resources: Financial And Human

While the population's health needs are becoming more complex, the health workforce in place to serve them is insufficient. Mali has one of the lowest densities of doctors, nurses and midwives in the world: 0.52 per 1,000 population, which is far below the WHO recommendation of 2.3 per 1,000 population.⁷ Geographic disparities in human resources for health densities are equally notable across the country, with health worker ratios of 5 or less per 10,000 in seven of the eleven regions, and 45% of all health professionals based in Bamako.⁸

The pipeline for human resources in health appears to be constricting in recent years, with numbers of new recruits decreasing sharply from 456 in 2013 to under 250 between 2015 and 2017, while the number of health professionals retiring increased.⁹

There is strong evidence of the cost-effectiveness of deploying community health workers to improve access to care and increase service utilization, with returns on investment as high as 10:1 according to a WHO analysis.¹⁰ Across a range of settings, CHWs were found to be particularly cost-effective at delivering services to tackle priority health challenges, such as tuberculosis, malaria, and reproductive, maternal, newborn, and child health.¹¹ CHWs are an important strategy to overcome health worker shortages, as well as to provide equitable access to health services in hard to reach areas, accelerating progress towards the health SDGs.

The Community Health Workforce in Mali, called ASCs (Agents de Santé Communautaire), is currently small and donor-dependent. The country lacks a robust national ASC program that can provide harmonized training and supervision, adequate working conditions and sustainable financial support, as well as ensure ASC coverage across all regions of the country.

The Government of Mali significantly divested from its primary healthcare sector following the Bamako Initiative, shifting much of the financial burden to users by charging service fees. Based on the latest available national budget estimates, Mali spent only 1.2% of its GDP and 5.1% of its national budget on healthcare in 2019 (LFI 2019), and only 0.04% of its GDP and 0.2% of its national budget specifically on primary health care in 2018. This budget allocation is insufficient compared to the international minimum standard of 5% GDP to health and is contributing to the country’s underperforming healthcare system. The Malian healthcare sector, particularly the PHC sector, is in need of urgent investment.

Access To Quality Care

User fees represent a major financial barrier to health care access in Mali. Nearly half (46%) of Malians in need of health care reported not going to a health center because it was too expensive.¹² Many Malians are unable to afford healthcare and can be forced to choose between borrowing, spending scarce resources, or going without treatment. Mali has one of the lowest rates of health expenditure in the world; a rate that decreased from USD \$40 to \$30 per capita between 2013 and 2016. More than a third of this spending (35%) comes from out of pocket (OOP) expenditures.¹³ These costs can be catastrophic to the financial wellbeing of vulnerable families living below the poverty line, which make up nearly half of Mali’s 19 million people.¹⁴ In 2015 alone, more than 400,000 individuals were impoverished from OOP health expenditures, which corresponds to a 2.3% increase in the national poverty headcount.¹⁵

Figure 4: Impoverishment due to OOP Health Expenditure

Source: World Bank Calculations based on ELIM (2006), and EMOP (2011, 2013, 2014, and 2015).

Figure 5: Health Spending per capita

Health spending per capita, US \$				
	Estimated spending, 2013		Estimated spending, 2016	
		In %, 2013		In %, 2016
Total	40	100%	30	100%
Government spending	6	14%	9	32%
External Donors	12	29%	10	32%
OOP	22	53%	11	35%

Source: WHO Health Expenditure Database 2016, accessed 2019

When a patient is able to reach a facility in Mali, the quality of the care they will receive is likely to be severely lacking due to inadequate personnel, infrastructure, materials, and services. Recent DHIS data found that only a quarter (25%) of CSCComs have access to a reliable source of water, a problem that is geographically concentrated, with 93% of CSCComs without water serving rural populations.¹⁶ There currently appears to be no central database or process for the routine collection of data on electricity and sanitation.

A survey on the operational capacity found that only 34% of all health facilities in the country (and 31% of all CSCComs) were found to have all essential equipment, including a scale, thermometer, stethoscope, blood pressure cuff and light source, with rural facilities once again the worst off (28% with all essential equipment).¹⁷

In the priority areas of maternal and child health, it was found that an average health facility in Mali possesses only 70% of the critical materials for prenatal care, including personnel, medications and diagnostic tests, and only 4% of facilities surveyed had all the basic elements for prenatal care. In addition, only 74% of facilities offered intermittent basic infant vaccination, and only one of the CSCCom-level facilities surveyed had all basic elements for child health care.¹⁷

The referral process between the different tiers of the healthcare system is also inadequate, with many people seeking care directly at higher levels, creating bottlenecks and inefficiencies throughout the system.

Laboratory and Diagnostic Services

High-performing laboratory services are a backbone of the primary health care system, providing clinicians with the tools and information they need to properly screen for diseases and optimize treatment, avoiding the serious risks of symptom-based clinical diagnosis without laboratory confirmation.^{18,19} Strengthening these systems would improve the diagnosis and management of six of the ten most common diseases presenting to PHC clinics, helping to fill major gaps in care.²⁰ Laboratory services and diagnostics also have an economic value tied to gains in efficiency or effectiveness.

Moreover, improving these systems will also strengthen other vital health systems functions. Actionable data is generated by diagnostic testing systems that facilitate effective epidemiological surveillance, outbreak and antimicrobial drug resistance detection, and planning and monitoring clinical activities, including health priorities like tuberculosis. Disease-specific registries (e.g., cancer or diabetes) are also a rich source of health system data informed by diagnostic testing.

Current international health guidelines identify laboratory services as a core capacity of health systems, and it is recommended that all WHO Member States develop and maintain such services, particularly to support their goal of achieving Universal Health Coverage (UHC).

An Essential Lab Services/Test list has been specified by the WHO²¹, however, the availability and use of these diagnostic tests and services in the Malian context, particularly at front line health centers and CSRefs, is extremely challenged, and this limits effective Last Mile health care delivery. Issues of funding, equipment supply, maintenance, reagent procurement, and stocks severely undermine its ability to serve the national healthcare sector and meet the growing diagnostic-clinical demand.

A national survey of health facility operational readiness found that diagnostic tests were the element most often lacking, with only 37% of facilities possessing all the recommended diagnostic tests. Diagnostic test availability was found to be an issue at all levels of the health system: inadequate in 47% of CSComs, 64% of CSRefs and 54% of national referral hospitals.¹⁷

Many private and below-scale private laboratory companies have emerged to meet this need and are occupying a growing share of the market. Their inflated fees constitute a significant and often catastrophic out of pocket expense for many Malian families.

Pharmaceutical and Medical Consumable Procurement And Distribution

Health system performance is influenced by the functioning of national supply chains and procurement processes for pharmaceuticals, vaccines, and other vital health products. These elements make up a significant share of health expenditures in low-resource settings facing complex disease burdens, and therefore improving the systems to deliver them presents opportunities for cost savings and gains in efficiency.

Functional centralized procurement and stock management systems, combined with ordering processes that are localized and decentralized, can improve efficiencies and reduce costs related to stockouts, wastage, and spoilage. Strengthening efforts will also improve access to pharmaceutical and medical products essential for the delivery of quality care and improved health outcomes.²²

In Mali, the PPM service - Pharmacie Populaire du Mali – is a parastatal entity established to aggregate CSCom and CSRef demand, provide competitive pricing, and distribute products effectively at scale. However, the PPM currently faces several challenges, including inefficient processes for international sourcing and procurement of medical stock, inadequate quantification and planning schemes, inefficient warehousing and stock staging, inefficient and costly distribution systems, frequent stockouts, and very importantly, no last mile delivery to CSComs.²³ As a result of these performance

issues, the PPM is not commercially competitive and charges higher rates than private wholesalers, and therefore controls an increasingly smaller percentage of the market, currently estimated around 25%.

The failure of the PPM to provide competitive pricing and work constructively with CSComs has resulted in the proliferation of private pharmacies and market dominance from a handful of private wholesalers. The private sector pharmacy space is expanding rapidly in geographical reach across the country, providing a more reliable supply of commodities, opening alternative distribution channels and, increasingly, providing para-medical care, such as giving medical advice and administering injections. This shift has occurred despite sub-optimal legislation and regulatory conditions, which has led to concerns related to the reliability of drugs, particularly the sale of counterfeit, expired or poorly stored products. Further regulation is required to provide both an enabling legal environment and appropriate controls and oversights for safety.

In summary, the health care system in Mali is undercapitalized, under-staffed and under-supplied, particularly at the primary healthcare level, and therefore incapable of ensuring a minimum standard of care for its population. Many foundational parts of the system are weak and in need of strengthening, such as the laboratory, diagnostics, drug supply chain systems. All these challenges point to a sector in crisis, and unable to deliver services in an increasingly complex national context.

1.2 Trends Impacting the Healthcare System

Demographic Changes

The Malian healthcare system is under pressure from a number of national and regional trends. First among these is the country's growing population, which has increased at an average rate of 3% between 2005 and 2015 – a faster pace than other countries of a comparable income level.⁷ This trend is projected to continue over the coming decade (figure 6). Mali's population is also youthful (approximately 66% under the age of 25) and is increasingly moving to urban centers.

Figure 6: Population Projections in Mali, 2020 through 2030

Mali Direction Nationale de la Population. WB urbanization rate estimate. UN World Population Prospects, 2018.

The lack of basic quality healthcare hampers the country’s economic and social development. The 2019 World Development Report ²⁴ emphasized the need for countries to invest urgently in the human capital of their people - particularly in education and in health - to cope with the changing nature of work and to reap the benefits of technological innovations altering labor markets today and in the future.

According to the latest Human Capital Index, ²⁵ Mali ranks near the bottom with an index of 0.32. This means that children born today in Mali will be on average 68% less productive than they could be if they had benefited from a complete education and good health during their childhood. In other words, the GDP per worker could be three times higher if the Malian population could benefit from both a good level of education and health.

While Mali has started its demographic transition (shifting towards lower mortality and fertility levels), the pace of the shift and the country’s economic growth are still too slow to reap the full benefits of its youthful population. More work in both health and development are needed to yield the full potential of Mali demographic dividend. ²⁶

Insecurity and Violence

Serious and evolving regional security concerns are greatly affecting the health of people living across the country. Providing access to quality essential services remains difficult in the north and center of the country, where responding to humanitarian needs currently trumps longer-term development objectives. This crisis has led to an acute inadequacy of medical personnel, drugs and other basic inputs, which has resulted in the declining function of health services in those affected regions, as well as important internal displacement and tragic loss of life.

A growing body of literature has shown that functioning social services are essential for ensuring peace and stability. Societies become particularly vulnerable to conflict and unrest when local institutions

breakdown or become inequitable.²⁷ Therefore, investing in health system strengthening is a vital part of the efforts to combat terrorism and violence in Mali, and an imperative in fragile areas in the north and center.

Environmental Stressors

Finally, Mali's location in the heart of the Sahel, along with factors of social, economic and environmental vulnerability, expose the country to several climate-related hazards, most notably droughts, floods, and locust invasion. Climate change is expected to exacerbate the impact of these dangers and make them more intense and severe. With more than 80 percent of Mali's population dependent on predominantly rain-irrigated agriculture for their livelihood, and agriculture accounting for more than 35 percent of GDP,²⁸ the potential impacts of rising temperature and rainfall variations in Mali are significant. These include heightened stress on food systems as well as an increased occurrence of malaria and diarrheal disease.

Responding to this crisis will require a "One Health" approach that will help to promote resilience as well as foster policy cooperation and coordination between the human and animal sectors for the earlier detection and effective response to infectious disease outbreaks, both in Mali and regionally.

In the past year, the Government of Mali has renewed its efforts to reform the healthcare system and turn around its struggling health indicators. This began with a process launched in February 2019 by the President of the Republic, Honorable Ibrahim Boubacar Keïta,²⁹ and evolved into the development of a nationally adapted Global Action Plan (GAP) for Healthy Lives and Well-being for All: the Mali Action Plan (MAP). The MAP is aligned with and will strengthen other national strategies, including the forthcoming National Health Sector Strategic Plan (PRODESS IV) and the current Strategic Framework for Economic Development (CREDD 2019-2023).

The MAP aims to accelerate the country's achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals by 2030, and to set the country on the path towards Universal Health Coverage. The investment needed now to implement the MAP is relatively small compared to the funds that have been spent over the last decade with limited impact. The benefits of timely and ambitious action for health will far outweigh its costs, and will lead to transformative social, political and human development for the country, as well as stability and resilience.

2. The Mali Action Plan (MAP): Mission and Vision

2.1 MAP Mission Statement

Health is a **human right**, a means to achieve **stability and security**, and an investment in **human capital and national growth** for Mali.

The Ministry of Health and Social Affairs, has developed the Mali Action Plan, in **continuity** with the reform announced in February 2019 and in alignment with the CREDD, with the goal of providing **sustainable, equitable and quality** health services to all its population, by **strengthening the main pillars** of the health system and by **mobilizing resources** to sustain improvements for generations to come.

The MAP, based on the principle of **human security**, will serve as the foundation for the next generation of PRODESS and the implementation of the RAMU.

2.2 The MAP Vision

Mali will become the **first country** to implement the **Global Action Plan** for Healthy Lives and Well-being for All, with primary health care as an entry point.

Mali will achieve the **greatest improvements in key health indicators in Africa by 2023**.

3. The MAP Guiding Principles

The MAP calls for a departure from “business as usual” as seen in Mali and across the African context in past decades. Its approach will utilize best international practices, adapt them for Malian culture and institutions, and thoughtfully draw lessons from similar efforts around the world.

Achieving lasting impact is essential in this effort, and as well as moving away from a legacy of vertical activities and programs toward integrated systems and actions.

These are the core principles guiding the design and implementation of the MAP at every stage:

- Rapid and accelerating action, immediate impact.
- Doubling down on access, removing financial, geographical barriers.
- Equity and inclusion: gender, ethnicity, socio-economic status.
- Innovation and technology leapfrogging.
- People-centered, community and civil society-led responses.
- Integration, harmonization, and alignment.
- Results based financing.
- Strong Malian leadership and ownership at the ministry, and mutual accountability.

4. The MAP Pillars

The MAP’s focus areas and activities are organized into four pillars, reaching across the depth and breadth of the national health system.

Figure 7: the MAP Pillars

4.1 Pillar I: Primary Health Care

4.1.1 Form a World-class Professionalized National CHW Cadre

Mali will form a national, professionalized, best-in-Africa Community Health Worker cadre, that will be deployed to provide free preventive and curative services at the doorstep of all those who need them. They will be the first point of contact for health education and treatment, as well as the starting point of an integrated CHW to CSCom referral pathway.

This new workforce will be mostly composed of women and offer female-friendly services. Their active presence in communities will also create synergistic social benefits, such as creating local employment, increasing gender participation, and providing strong female role models.

A first cohort will initially be recruited, trained and employed to work with communities served by 100 selected CSComs. The CHW workforce will then be progressively scaled to work all across the country.

4.1.2 Rehabilitate and Digitize the National CSCom Network

A completely rehabilitated and digitized CSCom network also be created, with refurbished facilities, reskilled and re-equipped staff, and with internet-connected and sustainably supplied systems with medicine and commodities defined in a basic service package.

Work will commence immediately, starting with 100 selected CSComs. The learning, experiences and systems developed during this initial phase of work will be used to inform an adaptive national rollout to the rest of the CSCom network over the following years.

These re-tooled CSComs will also provide a more efficient point in the referral system to higher levels of care.

4.1.3 Establish a Model Family Cluster Program

Mali will set up a Model Family Cluster (MFC) program, to strengthen community engagement in health and more effectively transmit empowering education and behavior change messages. Its slogan will be “Health Sector Reaching in, Community Reaching Out.”

It will be inspired by the “Model Families” at the center of Ethiopia’s successful Health Extension Program (HEP). To graduate to a model family, a household must adopt the government's 16 priority

interventions, which range from sleeping under a mosquito net to building separate latrines. Model families are awarded certificates and celebrated at village ceremonies – and in turn, asked to support five other households in adopting the priority interventions. This approach is based on the theory that innovations spread progressively, led by early adopters who can share their positive influence. The Ethiopian model was found to markedly improve contraceptive prevalence, immunization rates and antenatal care coverage.^{30,31}

Model Family Clusters across Mali will be offered family-focused training on healthy behaviors such as hygiene and sanitation, accessing services, family planning, infant feeding practices, and nutrition. They will form a grassroots movement for taking charge of one’s own health and transforming communities.

4.1.4 Establish a Center of Excellence in Primary Health Care

The work undertaken in this pillar will generate rich and original learning about primary healthcare system strengthening. This creates an opportunity to harness this knowledge and expertise, and disseminate it to the broader global health community, through the creation of a Center of Excellence in Primary Health Care (PHC) in Mali. This will be undertaken in collaboration with the World Health Organization and other international partners, including world-class academic institutions.

Like other models seen around the world, a Center of Excellence is a specialized program within a healthcare institution that supplies exceptionally high concentrations of expertise and related resources centered on particular medical areas and delivered in a comprehensive, interdisciplinary fashion.³²

Mali’s Center of Excellence in PHC will be instrumental in developing national quality improvement systems and promoting PHC in other Malian institutions. This will include creating a system for minimum standards and basic accreditation for CSComs, with metrics such as physical infrastructure and equipment, adherence to basic service package delivery, customer and employee satisfaction, quality of service, affordability, gender participation and responsiveness and health indicator improvement.

4.2. Pillar II: Secondary Health Care

4.2.1 Reform the “1 plus 7 Referral Hospital Network”

Seven referral hospitals will be completely refurbished. They will receive comprehensive improvements to their physical infrastructure and equipment, their service delivery platforms, their human resource training, and their systems’ digitalization and data connections. The referral network of these hospitals will be based on a thorough review of criteria, including service readiness, geographical location and demographic variables.

This reform work will be the foundation of the “1 plus 7 Referral Hospital Network,” which will connect the enhanced secondary healthcare structures up to the Gabriel Touré teaching hospital in Bamako for the provision of advanced care. It will also complement and amplify the transformation of the CCom network.

4.2.2 Support the Ongoing Rehabilitation of the Gabriel Touré Teaching Hospital in Bamako

The MAP will support the ongoing investment and infrastructure upgrade of the Gabriel Touré teaching hospital, which will reestablish it as a modernized and high-performing national referral hospital.

4.2.3 Create a New Surgery Skills Initiative

It has been found that six to seven percent of all preventable deaths worldwide are due to inadequate training and skills in only 44 basic surgical procedures. Investing the resources needed to provide these surgical interventions has also been found to be highly cost-effective and practical, even in low-resource settings.³³

In response to the unmet need for life-saving surgeries in Mali, a new Surgery Skills Initiative will be launched. It will involve designing an essential surgery package and equipping the facilities in the 1 Plus 7 referral Hospital Network to perform them. Once established, the package and training curricula from its initial deployment will be expanded across to the entire CSRef network.

4.3. Pillar III: Diagnostic and Laboratory Services

4.3.1 Rehabilitate the National Laboratory and Diagnostics Network

Mali’s national laboratory and diagnostics network will be fully rehabilitated, starting with each selected facility in the 1 plus 7 referral network and reaching down to the CCom level.

At its core will be a high-performing national laboratory with the technical and logistical capacity to provide a full range of diagnostic tests and receive referrals from across the country.

4.3.2 Strengthen the RESAOLAB Network

The West African Network of Clinical Laboratories (RESAOLAB) is the first regional program in West Africa to respond to the need for clinical biology systems that provide high-quality services - a traditionally underfunded area of public health. Mali was a founding member at its launch in 2009, along with other West African Health Organization (WAHO) members, which now include Benin, Burkina Faso, Guinea, Niger, Senegal, and Togo.

RESAOLAB has been pioneering in strengthening national laboratories and their regional network, improving the quality of biomedical services and science, and advocating for their central place in health systems. Mali will build upon the catalytic work of the network, and lead efforts to mobilize additional donor funds to sustain and amplify its activities.

4.3.3 Improve Synergies with Private Laboratory Services

A number of high-performing private sector laboratories will be identified to provide supportive operational management and service support to the public sector. These new synergies will be guided by government regulation and oversight and allow for the introduction of best practices in training, equipment maintenance and supply systems.

4.3.4 Explore Starting a New RTD Manufacturing Line in Bamako

There is a growing demand for rapid diagnostic tests (RTDs), with approximately 280 million used per year globally, of which approximately 66% are used in African countries. Malaria tests, which are an important diagnostic product consumed in the region, were mostly (75%) rapid diagnostic tests (RDT).³⁴ An Africa-based manufacturing of RDT's is technologically, economically and industrially desirable for routine tests, annual campaigns, and national programs, such as for malaria, HIV, and women's health (e.g. pregnancy and STI's), as well as for more ad-hoc responses to infectious disease outbreaks such as yellow fever or Ebola.

Mali will actively pursue the opportunity to participate in the emerging Gate-EIB sponsored PPP diagnostics initiative and to utilize it as a beacon and template for other health sector area PPP's in Mali.

4.3.5 Strengthen the newly created National Public Health Institute for Mali

National public health institutes (NPHIs) are science-based governmental organizations, which function as coordinating entities for all public health activities in their host country and internationally. They serve a vital role in centralizing, informing and operationalizing health system responses, such as to new epidemics or natural disasters.

Mali recently created a National Public Health Institute to enhance the leadership and capabilities of its national preparedness and response systems. It will consolidate and align the work of several existing government public health institutions, including the Center for Vaccine Development, the National Center for Disease Control, the National Center for Public Health Research, and the Center for Study of Child Survival. It will be provided with appropriate staff, logistical infrastructure and a clear mandate to act in cases of emergency.

The NPHI in Mali will coordinate the national strategic surveillance system, to give the Malian government timely information on the causes of death and disease, as well as the deployment of healthcare resources and other critical assets. It will also reinforce existing laboratory capacity in microbiology, immunology and pathology to test for dangerous pathogens, safely handle specimen transport within the country and to international referral centers.

4.4 Pillar IV: Pharmacy Procurement and Distribution

4.4.1 Overhaul the PPM system

Mali's national pharmaceutical and medical product supply chain systems, beginning with the PPM, will be restructured to be more efficient, timely, data-informed, cost-competitive, and responsive to the needs of the health care sector, particularly the CSCoM network.

A centralized procurement and stock management system will be created and combined with localized and decentralized ordering processes. In addition, a more competitive and synergistically engineered relationship between the PPM, private wholesalers, and public health facilities will also be developed to serve the national interest.

4.4.2. Develop New Last Mile Drug and Medical Consumable Delivery Solutions

Special efforts will be made to ensure upgrades to national supply chain systems are able to reach down to the CSCoM level. Additional regional warehouses and logistics capacity may also be embedded in hospitals, as indicated by the PPM audit and restructuring work.

5. The MAP Delivery approaches

Figure 8: the MAP Pillars and Delivery Approaches

5.1 Last Mile Service Delivery

Maliens live and get sick in the last mile reached by the health care system. Therefore, the MAP will focus on continuous, institutionalized last mile delivery of care. This will structure services around providing behavior change communication, diagnoses, treatments and referrals at the doorstep of those who need them. It will help to bridge geographic barriers to care, bringing it to the most vulnerable, fastest-growing, most in-need communities.

5.2 Differentiated Approaches to Healthcare

The MAP will also use differentiated service delivery approaches, with a focus on location and population characteristics and avoiding using “one size fits all.”

This will involve responding to regional needs, such as improving the resilience of the health system in the north and center of the country through humanitarian emergency action and consolidating the health system in the south.

Figure 9: Unmet need for contraception among women aged 15-49 (% by region)

Figure 10: Stunting rates among children under age 5 (% by region)

Graphique 7.9 Besoins non satisfaits, par région

Pourcentage de femmes de 15-49 ans actuellement en union ayant des besoins non satisfaits en matière de planification familiale

Graphique 11.3 Retard de croissance chez les enfants, par région

Pourcentage d'enfants de moins de 5 ans qui présentent un retard de croissance

Source: EDSM IV¹

5.3 Rapid-Impact Interventions for Priority Populations

The MAP will deploy “quick-win,” rapid impact interventions for priority populations. These will be identified based on their feasibility and impact on the burden of disease. They will be focused on addressing the concerns of the most vulnerable: mothers and children under five; as well as those most amenable to preventative interventions: youth in the second decade of life.

5.4 Integrated Fiduciary Management

The MAP also recognizes the changing financial and technical partner landscape as well as the need for a more efficient and aggressively coordinated use of existing funds.

A newly established Basket Fund entity within the MOHSA was decreed in 2019 and will act as an administrative and fiduciary aggregating mechanism for a variety of partner funds including the WB, GF, GAVI and others. Over time all partner funds will be aggregated through, directed, and managed by the Basket Fund. The Fund will initially consist of a series of sub PIU’s (Project Implementation Units) with dedicated resources and staffing for the management of partner mandates. Over time these PIU’s will be folded up into one aggregate PIU with shared staffing, administrative resources and costs. The PIU will have a fiduciary and financial oversight role only in the allocation of funds and periodic reporting on fund distribution.

Figure 11: MAP Basket Fund and Management Unit

Source: Internal MOHSA

5.5 Dedicated Strategy and Operations Unit

The establishment of key human resource capacity within the MOHSA to drive the MAP is essential and will be embedded in the formation of a special operations “MAP Management Unit”. The MAP Management Unit will be a high-level strategy formation and operational management group, formed and utilized by the MOHSA to provide the expertise and capacity required to flesh-out the design of and implement the MAP. It will be responsible for directing the activities of the PIU and function as one seamless administrative entity, reporting directly to the Minister of health and Social Affairs. Once formed, the unit will be increasingly staffed by Malians trained through this unique national initiative and become a unique and valuable national healthcare management asset.

6. The MAP Enablers

To bolster the pillars and delivery approaches of the MAP, several “Enablers” have been identified – which will be leveraged to enhance its design and facilitate its implementation.

Figure 12: The MAP Pillars, Delivery Approaches and Enablers

6.1. Financing and National Health Insurance

The size, consistency, and reliability of health financing is a fundamental concern for maintaining the desired pace and sustainability of the MAP reform, particularly for areas that require significant capital expenditure, staffing and technology inputs.

6.1.1 Domestic Resources

Economic growth is expected to continue despite the unrest, with real GDP growth estimated at approximately 4.7% in 2019, down only slightly from previous years.³⁵ The government will strive to increase its contribution of GDP to health, despite the competing demands placed on national budgets due to the instability in the north and center.

6.1.2 Innovative Financing Mechanisms

In addition, the tremendous potential from alternative health system financing mechanisms will be explored and utilized with help from the World Bank, the Global Financing Facility, the Islamic Development Bank, French Development Bank, the European Union and other international agencies.

Specifically, an actionable analysis of the additional fiscal space available in Mali is an important priority, particularly related to targeted taxes on specific sectors and improved mechanisms of collection – for example the mining, mobile sector, aspects of the sin, beverages and plastics sectors that have negative health consequences.

Additionally, as Mali's debt burden is growing and likely to continue so for the foreseeable future, the potential exists to financially engineer debt for health equity swaps and buy-downs, under appropriate 3rd party oversight, informed by the experience of other countries.

Lastly, the harnessing of the goodwill and financial resources of the diaspora is also vital. Many Malians currently living abroad are already involved in personal or village initiatives or are interested in assisting their communities in some way. Government Bonds could be marketed to the diaspora, who are likely to accept lower interest and longer maturity than private investors. Strategic engagement and communication with the Malian diaspora could lead to a modality for the aggregation of their concerns and potential to participate in initiatives that can directly enhance the social wellbeing of their families and communities. Health and community services is an obvious intervention with immediate impact. A third-party investment entity, health foundation, or diaspora bonds could be created to absorb and transparently deploy this financial good will.

6.1.3 Results-Based Financing

The Government of Mali, with World Bank support, is working to scale-up Results-Based Financing (RBF) across the health care system. The aim of RBF at the primary care level is to increase the coverage and the quality of an essential package of services.

RBF is a payment system founded on improving performance and quality of care. Instead of allocating inputs such as physical and human resources through central planning alone, it allocates financial resources to frontline health facilities based on results achieved to enhance the availability, accessibility and quality of essential services. PBF is implemented to address critical impediments confronting the delivery of services at frontline health facilities. These challenges include: the shortage of funds to meet operating expenses; the lack of autonomy to manage resources to procure drugs and attract and motivate qualified human resources; the lack of focus on results and limited use of performance data at all levels; and the lack of accountability and transparency in the health system. PBF has been associated with improvements in both the quantity and the quality of services provided and therefore provides an opportunity for the Malian healthcare system to gain in efficiency and effectiveness.^{36,37,38}

6.1.4 National Health Insurance

Contributory schemes in Mali are fragmented and cover only part of the population. Formal sector employees and civil servants are covered by the *Assurance Maladie Obligatoire* (AMO) (insuring 16% of the population), a mandatory health insurance scheme managed by the Caisse Nationale d'Assurance Maladie (CANAM) a semi-autonomous government agency under the authority of the Ministry of Health and Social Affairs. A large share of the population is included in voluntary health insurance schemes (AMV) for the informal and agricultural sectors. Finally, a non-contributory scheme, the Régime d'Assurance Médicale (RAMED) also exists for indigents.

There are 193 Community Based Health Insurance (CBHI) or *Mutuelles* schemes targeting the informal sector and cover only 5% of the population. This is seen as an important tool to increase the percentage of the population covered by health insurance.

In 2018, the Malian government passed the Regime D'Assurance Maladie Universelle (RAMU) law. The objective of the RAMU law is to institute a universal health insurance regime that will cover a basic package of services to all residents of Mali. The RAMU will be administered by the CANAM and will integrate all existing schemes i.e. AMO, the CBHI schemes and RAMED, under one umbrella. The RAMU will be administered by the CANAM which was previously in charge of administering the AMO. Importantly, major implementation aspects of the RAMU still need to be defined and regulated by a government decree, including the package of services, the contribution and insurance coverage rates.

There is potential to grow the CBHI base, particularly in the rapidly expanding urban areas where the informal sector is increasingly dominant. There is an opportunity to address the health needs of this community in a targeted way, as they have both marginally higher disposable income and greater OOP expenditures, and to draw them into a demonstrably improved health product offering.

6.2 International Partnerships

In 2012, funding from external donors accounted for 69% of total health expenditures in Mali, with an estimated \$432 million (USD) spent by external donors.³⁹ A preliminary mapping of the top donor contributions to the health sector between 2017 and 2020 shows that donor spending remains significant although plateaued in recent years.

After several years of decreased donor funding for health, projected donor funding for 2019 was expected to increase by 20% from the previous year, from \$234.2 million dollars (USD) in 2018 to \$281.8 million in 2019. This was driven primarily by an increase in funding from the Global Fund, GAVI and UNICEF.

The MOHSA must ask the donor community to align and increase their commitments to the MAP to ensure its robust implementation.

6.3. Governance

6.3.1 MOHSA Structure and Processes

The Ministry of Health and Social Affairs (MOHSA) is currently under-resourced and lacking key expertise. Many structural inefficiencies exist which render the institution less able to respond to systems improvement needs today and anticipate future problems.

For example, many hours and funds go into an elaborate planning process at all levels of the ministry, however, much of this process is not mission critical, timely or relevant as an input to the planning and decision processes within the ministry and health sector more broadly.

Moreover, current planning processes also do not sufficiently account for accelerating population growth, population distribution and rapid urbanization. As a result, rapidly growing and transient communities in and peripheral to urban areas are left without adequate water and sanitation and are heavily congested.

A general restructuring of the MOH should be undertaken, informed by past work undertaken by the Ministry of Reform, an updated mapping MOH current resources, structures and processes, and a prioritization of resources and needs.

6.3.2 ASACO Governance and Management

Many ASACOs are failing to fulfill one of their fundamental functions: engaging, involving and representing the community they serve, particularly with regard to proportionate female involvement, as recommended in the FENASCOM Charter. Only 35% of the ASACO meet the recommended female involvement in the Board and solely 2% are chaired by a woman. Without constant, systematic pressure to satisfy the community's expectations of affordable quality health care, governance is weak. Twenty-four per cent of ASACOs are considered nonfunctional as they are failing to hold regular board meetings. Many ASACO governance bodies have little or no training and are ill prepared for the management, growth and stabilization of an increasingly complex health delivery. These limitations of governance, general and financial management hamper or limit the ability of the CSCOM to deliver affordable quality healthcare. Many ASACO also do not conduct effective financial control and/or publish transparent voting, management or financial documents and statement of accounts.

Lastly, the national association, the FENASCOM does not seem to maintain consolidated accounts or practice regular financial or quality assurance audits on the ASACO, nor enforce and/or monitor minimum standards or capitalization and stability audits. There is limited oversight and no ultimate accountability, leading to a significant proportion of ASACOs that are non-functional.

A comprehensive reform of the governance and management of the national ASACO network and the FENASCOM must be done imperatively and be a condition for moving ahead with the CSCOM refurbishment work.

6.4. Private Sector Engagement

6.4.1 Strategic Public-Private Partnerships

The Private sector has traditionally been viewed narrowly, as a source of research funding and commercialization for health, or negatively, as something to be sidelined during policy formulation and service delivery planning. Nevertheless, private sector service delivery has continuously expanded across African countries, despite a lack of formal government support and facilitation, as a response to deficiencies in the public sector.

Even in countries that have created an enabling legislative environment, it is rare to find coordinated public-private initiatives informed by a long-term strategy to increase the cost-effectiveness and affordability of service coverage. Many governments are now beginning to understand that the provision of affordable PHC and eventually UHC will place demands on capital, management and operations that government resources and capacity alone cannot realistically meet.

Mali has a unique history of private sector engagement in areas traditionally reserved exclusively for the public sector, including primary health care, district hospitals and pharmacy management. It is therefore ideally positioned to lead the way in health sector public-private partnerships (PPP's), and the MAP should support multi-sectoral efforts to engage constructively with the private sector.

6.4.2 Improved business environment

An improved business environment should be created in Mali, including appropriate laws, regulations, and incentives, which will facilitate the controlled growth of the private health sector.

Importantly, the aim of this renewed engagement with the private sector is not to privatize the healthcare system, but rather to strengthen its private segment in order to leverage it to rehabilitate and improve public services, by introducing greater efficiency, new practices, advanced technology and quality improvements, particularly in areas prioritized by the MAP.

6.5. Innovation and Digital Health

6.5.1 Digital Health Technologies

Carefully selected and designed e-health or m-health digital platforms should be embedded when appropriate throughout the health system, from hand-held data collection devices for CHWs, to electronic medical records at CSRefs, to data dashboards for district decision makers. These systems will provide a rich routine data to inform decision making and surveillance. Their proper utilization will also help health workers to be more efficient and provide better quality of care with fewer errors and waste. The use of technologies to save lives and money should be explored at every opportunity.

6.5.2 Integrated Health Technologies

In addition to systems level technology enhancements, selected CSComs could be equipped with technologies such as telemedicine, artificial intelligence and clinical decision support software and automated dispensing, in order to carefully test the usability and cost-effectiveness of these systems, in order to potentially bring them to scale.

6.5.3 PHC Clinic in a Box Prototypes

Finally, the MAP will also explore how prototypes of “clinics in a box” could be used in Mali. Such models involve either building or renovating a Primary Health Care facility, usually within an underserved community.

Modular clinics can be made of cheap, rapidly adjustable materials (typically converted shipping containers), and offer a low-cost way to rapidly expand of the network of health facilities. Several different versions could be compared to access their feasibility and usability, and to estimate the cost of infrastructure, equipment and operations.

7. The MAP Impacts

Mali aims to directly and immediately address the health crisis and to accelerate the country’s achievement of SDG-3, “good health and wellbeing.” The MAPs key impact targets to reach by 2030 include ⁴⁰:

- Reducing the maternal mortality rate to 234 per 100,000 live births.
- Averting 208,000 cases of anemia among women of reproductive age.
- Saving 209,000 lives of children under 5.
- Saving 58,000 lives of children under 5 from malaria.
- Averting 12,000 cases of stunting among of children under 5.
- Reducing unmet need for contraception to under <1 %.

A more comprehensive set of MAP impact targets are structured around components of SGD 3 on two different time horizons (in figure 8 below).

Figure 8: MAP Impact targets by SDG 3 sub-component

Mali Goal 2023	Mali Goal 2030
<p>3.1.1: By 2023, reduce the global maternal mortality ratio to 299 per 100,000 live birth.</p> <p>3.1.2: By 2023, increased the proportion of births attended by skilled health personnel to 73.4%.</p>	<p>3.1.1: By 2030, reduce the global maternal mortality ratio to 234 per 100,000 live birth.</p> <p>3.1.2: By 2030, increased the proportion of births attended by skilled health personnel to 85%.</p>
<p>3.2.1: By 2023, reduce U5 mortality to at least as low as 87 per 1,000 live births.</p> <p>3.2.2: By 2023, reduce neonatal mortality to at least as low as 31 per 1,000 live births.</p>	<p>3.2.1: By 2030, reduce U5 mortality to at least as low as 65 per 1,000 live births.</p> <p>3.2.2: By 2030, reduce neonatal mortality to at least as low as 26 per 1,000 live births.</p>
<p>3.3.1: By 2023, reduce the incidence of AIDS to 0.65 per 1,000 population.</p> <p>3.3.2: By 2023, reduce the incidence of TB to 41 per 1,000 population.</p> <p>3.3.3: By 2023, reduce the incidence of malaria to 67 per population.</p>	
<p>3.7.1: By 2023, have up to 30% of women age 15 - 49 have access to a modern method of contraception.</p> <p>By 2030, Reducing unmet need for contraception to 10%.</p>	<p>3.7.1: By 2030, have up to 41% of women age 15 - 49 have access to a modern method of contraception.</p> <p>By 2030, Reducing unmet need for contraception to under <1 %.</p>
<p>9.9.b1: By 2030, have up to 65% of children age 12 - 23 months receive all the basic vaccines.</p>	

In the long term, the implementation of the MAP will also contribute to meeting the population’s demand for access to quality healthcare and services, restoring popular confidence in national health services, removing barriers and increasing service utilization, and improving health outcomes across the country.

Conclusion

The MAP is guided by a vision of a better future for the people of Mali, one which respects their right to health, protects their human security, and develops their full potential. It aims to position the country at the forefront of equitable progress and community-driven innovation, and to achieve a dramatic turnaround in the country's health indicators. It is at the center of a robust effort to meet the commitment to achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by 2030 and to work towards Universal Health Care with the goal of 100 – 100 – 50 – PLUS.

The MAP will help the health system better respond to the rapidly evolving national context and provide rapid-impact solutions that are responsive to differences in populations and locations and reach to the last mile. It will enable the efficient, integrated and strategic management of funds and operations in order to maximize the benefits of every XOF spent.

It is now up to all of the actors involved to seize the opportunity before us, to benefit from the strong political leadership, and to apply the learning from all across the world to this effort. The implementation of the MAP will require the unfailing commitment of everyone involved in health and social development and will ensure an improved quality of life of our families and our fellow citizens.

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